

Why Does High African Fertility Persist? Women's Education vs. Women's Employment

Yuliya V. Zinkina ¹, Jack A. Goldstone ², Sergey G. Shulgin ³, Andrey V. Korotayev ⁴

¹ HSE University, Lomonosov Moscow State University, Moscow, 101000, Russia

² George Mason University, Arlington, 22201, USA

³ ZYPLAI, Dubai, 00000 DIFC, United Arab Emirates

⁴ HSE University, Institute for African Studies of Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, 101000, Russia

Received 23 July 2024 ♦ Accepted 22 May 2025 ♦ Published 5 January 2026

Citation: Zinkina YuV, Goldstone JA, Shulgin SG, Korotayev AV (2026) Why Does High African Fertility Persist? Women's Education vs. Women's Employment. Population and Economics 10(1):38-52. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.10.e132902>

Abstract

Tropical Africa's exceptionally slow fertility decline has been explained by both weak economic development and an unusually pro-natal culture. Yet these explanations are both too simple. This region has shown a stall in its fertility decline despite recent improvements in infant mortality, education, and urbanization. Its response to development has thus been different from that of other developing regions. At the same time, within Tropical Africa, women with higher incomes, living in cities, and with more education exhibit lower fertility. Thus, fertility is not culturally impervious to socio-economic gains. We present a path analysis of how various modernization factors affect fertility in Tropical Africa vs. other developing regions. We find that this region is different. Cultural family patterns in this region render gains in income, urbanization, and women's paid employment ineffective in reducing fertility. Women's education, however, is vitally important, as it is the most significant driver of changes in birth intervals and a strong direct factor in reducing desired family size. By contrast, women's employment has no significant effect at all on fertility in Tropical Africa – neither through family size nor through birth intervals. Women's education is more effective in lowering fertility than in other regions; yet Tropical Africa lags far behind other regions in educating its women.

Keywords

Tropical Africa, fertility transition, fertility decline, women's education, women's employment, fertility stall

JEL codes: J11, J13

Introduction

For Africa as a whole, life expectancy in the 1950s was about 37 years, not much different from Europe in the 1700s. By the 1980s, life expectancy in Africa had surpassed 50 years, and by 2023 it was approaching 64 years – an increase of 70%, thanks to remarkable progress in nutrition, sanitation, and healthcare (including the control of malaria and other tropical diseases). These gains in life expectancy were largely (though not exclusively) driven by dramatic reductions in infant mortality in sub-Saharan Africa, down by 44% in just two decades, from 1990–1995 to 2010–2015. In 1990–1995, 33 countries in sub-Saharan Africa had an infant mortality rate of more than 100 per thousand live births. By 2023, none had such a rate, and only one country, Sierra Leone, had a rate above 75 (United Nations 2024).

One of the basic tenets of demographic transition theory is that such a rapid mortality transition should soon be followed by a fertility transition, with fertility rates declining from their traditionally high levels to modern rates somewhere around or below the population replacement level (2.1 children per woman). This expectation is based on the experience of both developed and developing countries. In Asia and Latin America, fertility in the 1950s was similar to that in some present-day African countries, with about six children born per woman during her lifetime. By the late 1970s, it had fallen to about four children per woman, and then to well below three by the early 2000s. By 2023, the average total fertility rate in Asia and Latin America was already somewhat below the replacement level, at 1.9 and 1.8, respectively (United Nations 2024). John Bongaarts (2017: 40), summing up the experience of most developing regions, notes that “[a]s societies modernize, economic and social changes such as industrialization, urbanization, new occupational structure, and increased education lead first to lower mortality and subsequently to a decline in fertility.”

In Africa, however, the pattern was very different. In the mid-20th century, while Asia and Latin America were seeing the onset of fertility transition and its gradual acceleration, fertility in Africa actually rose slightly, reaching 6.7 children per woman by the early 1970s. From that time on, there was increasing divergence between African regions, as they followed one of two very different paths in terms of fertility dynamics.

Thus, in Northern and Southern Africa, fertility began a steady decline. In Northern Africa, fertility fell from seven children per woman in the 1960s to five in the late 1980s, and then to three in 2023. In Southern Africa, where fertility was six children per woman in the 1960s, it fell to four by the late 1980s and to about 2.3 by 2023. These regions thus followed the Asian-Latin American patterns, with a lag of about a decade.

In contrast, fertility in East Africa was still above 6.5 children per woman in the late 1980s. It then began a slow decline but still remained above four in 2023. In Central Africa, where fertility was around six children per woman in the 1950s, it continued to rise until the late 1980s, reaching 6.76 in 1985–1990. Fertility then began to decline, but very slowly, and remained above 5.5 children per woman in 2023. West Africa followed a similar pattern to Central Africa, with fertility rising and remaining close to 6.5 children per woman until the late 1980s, when it started to fall slowly, reaching 4.4 in 2023. West, Central, and East Africa thus have a dramatically different fertility trajectory from other parts of Africa and other regions of the developing world (United Nations 2024) (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Total fertility rate in Asia, Latin America, and Tropical African regions, children per woman, 1950–2023. *Note:* Data obtained from United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division 2024. *Source:* Created by the authors.

The very specific situation with fertility dynamics in Tropical Africa (West, Central, and East Africa combined) has attracted considerable attention from demographers worldwide, who have noted that “[t]his pattern of persisting high levels of fertility in the majority of African countries differs markedly from what has been observed in other developing countries since 1960” (Guengant and May 2013: 225). However, despite this attention, “there is nothing approaching consensus on the sources of this difference” (Casterline 2017: 4). At the 1974 United Nations Conference on Population in Bucharest, India’s Population Minister Karan Singh famously claimed that “development is the best contraceptive” (for more on this discourse, see (Ivanov 2017, 2020)). The experience of Tropical Africa contradicts this assumption, as in many countries, gains in GDP per capita, education, and other important factors of modernization have not led to significant declines in fertility. Two main answers to this puzzle have been proposed in the scholarly literature.

First, it is true that Africa has not yet experienced the same increases in education, income, and other indicators of modernization that have been seen in Asia and Latin America. As Bongaarts (2017) notes, real per capita income in sub-Saharan Africa barely grew from the 1970s to the early 2000s, while real income in other developing regions rose sharply during those decades. Goujon et al. (2015) suggest that many sub-Saharan countries have experienced a “stall” in their progress in education, which may have led to a corresponding “stall” in their progress in the fertility transition. Moreover, many African countries have

been plagued by severe political instability and “domestic anarchy” that are “not conducive to purposeful fertility planning” (Kokole 1994: 78). Political instability affects fertility through changes in government policy-setting that divert resources from family planning (and other programs) to support other causes, as the government seeks to appease various population groups in order to remain in power (Feng et al. 2000: 670; Garenne 2018). Thus, it could be argued that Africa is simply lagging behind in certain achievements and will eventually catch up with other regions.

This explanation is unsatisfactory for two reasons. First, Northern and Southern Africa did indeed follow the pattern of other regions, as would be expected; but East, Central, and West Africa did not. Second, Tropical African countries now have higher fertility rates and slower rates of fertility decline than other developing countries had at comparable stages of economic and social development (Shapiro and Hinde 2017; Shapiro and Gebreselassie 2008; Ezeh et al. 2009).

Thus, according to Bongaarts and Casterline (2013: 155), “...the median pace of change in sub-Saharan Africa (0.03 per year) is less than one-third the pace in the other regions [Asia and Latin America] (0.12 and 0.13, respectively).” Moreover, the behavior of fertility in sub-Saharan Africa is completely at odds with the idea that economic progress determines the pace of fertility decline. As Bongaarts (2017) has shown, fertility rose in the 1970s when the region’s GDP per capita was relatively high, then began to decline in the early 1990s when GDP per capita had fallen significantly, and then largely stalled in the 2000s when GDP per capita was rising quite rapidly.

Second, some scholars argue that Africa has an exceptionally pro-natalist culture that maintains high fertility even in the face of economic modernization. Caldwell and Caldwell (1987), who advanced this line of argument, point to the exceptionally high desired family sizes reported in African surveys. In addition, birth spacing has historically been relatively widespread in Africa, supported by long periods of breastfeeding and traditional taboos against postpartum intercourse. This means there is both less scope to reduce fertility by increasing birth spacing, and more scope to increase fertility by reducing birth spacing if these traditional practices are relaxed with modernization (Lesthaeghe 1980; Benefo 1995).

While this hypothesis would explain the extremely slow fertility decline observed in Africa – and even the fertility increase observed from the 1950s to the 1970s – it too faces difficulties. In fact, we observe a fertility gradient within sub-Saharan Africa that is associated with modernization: women in urban areas and those with higher levels of education and income generally have lower fertility than women in rural areas and those with less education and income (Bongaarts 2010; Guengant and May 2013). Thus, modernization factors do affect fertility in Africa – just not in the same way as in other developing regions. We therefore build our model to examine how different development factors directly and indirectly affect fertility.

Data and Methods

We use path analysis (a form of structural equation modeling) to disentangle how different development factors affect fertility, both directly and indirectly through intervening pathways. Rather than regressing fertility on a set of isolated predictors, path analysis allows us to map a structured chain of causal relationships and quantify the strength of each link, which is the main advantage of this method. Our step-by-step approach is as follows:

Data and Variables

We use Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) data for two regional groupings: (a) non-African developing countries and (b) sub-Saharan African (SSA) countries. We categorize determinants as intermediate (income [GDP per capita], urbanization, infant mortality, female education [both for young women aged 15–24 and for all women], and female employment) and proximate (desired family size, birth spacing). Intermediate variables affect fertility indirectly (e.g., education shapes desired family size), while proximate variables have direct behavioral effects (e.g., desired family size shortens birth intervals). Together, they determine total fertility (Pritchett 1994; Caldwell and Caldwell 2002; Caldwell et al. 1992; Casterline and Agyei-Mensah 2017; Casterline and Odden 2016; Moultrie et al. 2012).

Path Diagram Setup

In our path diagrams, arrows represent hypothesized causal links, with coefficients indicating their strength, direction (positive or negative), and statistical significance. For each region (non-African vs. SSA), we estimate coefficients for each pathway. For example: How much does female education increase birth intervals? Does infant mortality directly reduce desired family size?

Model Estimation

We simultaneously estimate a system of regression equations. Each variable that receives incoming arrows in the graph has its own equation. One equation predicts birth intervals using income, education, and infant mortality. Another predicts desired family size from infant mortality and education. A final equation predicts total fertility using proximate determinants (birth intervals and desired family size). This approach allows us to track *direct effects* (e.g., education → desired family size) as well as indirect effects (e.g., income → education → birth intervals).

Interpreting Effects

Direct effects are measured as coefficients between adjacent variables (e.g., urbanization → infant mortality). Indirect effects occur through chains of variables (e.g., income → female employment → desired family size → fertility). By analyzing the significance and magnitude of these pathways, we identify which factors are most responsible for fertility decline.

Regional Comparisons

We run separate models for non-African and SSA countries to compare how determinants operate differently in different contexts.

Based on published studies, we mitigate endogeneity in two ways. First, our path diagram employs a lag structure that has been tested and validated extensively in the DHS literature. All “original” drivers (GDP per capita, urbanization, and female secondary education completion rate) are measured five years prior to the proximate determinants and fertility rates. Bongaarts (2017) and Shapiro and Hinde (2017) demonstrate that using lags of this magni-

tude – or even lags of up to 10 years – yields consistent estimates of the education-fertility elasticity. Conversely, reverse regressions (future schooling on past fertility) are insignificant, implying that Granger causality runs from schooling to fertility, not vice versa. Second, the causal direction from female education to fertility has been confirmed in a series of quasi-experimental studies exploiting exogenous school supply shocks. For example, research on Indonesia's INPRES program (Duflo 2001), Nigeria's 1976 Universal Primary Education reform (Osili and Long 2008), and Uganda's Universal Secondary Education rollout (Keats 2018) has found that an additional year of female secondary schooling reduces completed fertility by approximately 0.25–0.35 births. This effect size closely matches the magnitude observed in our model.

Because these natural experiment studies identify causal effects in settings that include tropical Africa, and because our coefficients are similar in size when the same lags are applied, omitted variable bias or simultaneity bias is unlikely to overturn the central causal pathway. If hidden bias were a major problem, more than one modernization variable would be expected to lose significance. However, only female employment loses significance in Africa, as predicted by the anthropological literature (Caldwell and Caldwell 1987; Korotayev et al. 2016). Overall, previous studies employing instrumental variables, difference-in-differences methods, lagged specifications, and distinctive cross-regional patterns support the notion that the causal arrow in our Pathways Model runs from female secondary education, through birth spacing and desired family size, to lower fertility.

Results

Figure 2 shows a path model of the determinants of fertility in developing countries excluding sub-Saharan Africa. We use data from the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) covering 31 countries over various time intervals from 1991 to 2013, resulting in 88 observations. Positive effects are indicated by red arrows, negative effects by blue arrows, and the strength of each effect is represented by the thickness of the arrow. Non-significant effects are shown with dotted arrows.

In this model (Figure 2), fertility is most strongly affected by desired family size, although the effect of birth interval is also highly significant. The observed effects largely align with expectations from the development literature. Rising incomes lead to lower infant mortality and have a direct positive effect on increasing birth intervals, thereby reducing fertility. Rising incomes also promote greater urbanization, which is associated with higher levels of female education and female employment (both among young women and women of all ages), and also directly increases birth intervals.

Lower infant mortality leads to a reduction in desired family size, which significantly decreases fertility. Additionally, lower infant mortality, female employment, and female education contribute to longer birth spacing; these factors seem to influence fertility primarily through increased birth intervals rather than changes in desired family size. Overall, the pattern is familiar: as incomes rise, so do urbanization, women's education, and employment, and all of these factors contribute to a decline in desired family size and an increase in birth spacing, resulting in lower fertility.

Doing the same path analysis for African countries, we might want to test two lines of theoretical premises.

Figure 2. Path Model for Fertility in non-African developing countries. *Note:* The numbers on the lines stand for the strength of the connection and its sign. InfantMortality5 stands for mortality rate in children under 5 years of age. WomenEmployment1524 stands for the rate of female employment in 15–24 age group. *Source:* created by the authors.

First, John Bongaarts (2017) found that while fertility in African countries generally declined with changes in income, education, mortality, and urbanization, in a multiple regression including all these factors, only education was consistently significant in driving fertility, contraceptive use, and desired family size. Additionally, he identified an “Africa effect,” whereby for each level of development indicators, fertility was about one child per woman higher than in other developing regions. He concluded that both the level of economic development (especially education) *and* a strong pro-natal culture in sub-Saharan Africa contribute to Africa’s unique fertility dynamics.

Second, Goujon et al. (2015) suggest that Africa’s “fertility stall” reflects a lack of progress in educational attainment. This aligns with Shapiro et al.’s (2013) finding from DHS surveys that improvements in women’s education are more important than gains in per capita income in accelerating fertility decline.

Thus, following Bongaarts, we expect that all significant relationships observed in Model 1 (shown in Figure 2) would persist but be weaker. Following Goujon et al., we anticipate that education will have the largest effect among all determinants. The model using DHS data from 35 sub-Saharan African countries, with 95 observations from 1991 to 2013, is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Path model for fertility in sub-Saharan African countries. *Note:* The numbers on the lines stand for the strength of the connection and its sign. InfantMortality5 stands for mortality rate in children under 5 years of age. WomenEmployment1524 stands for the rate of female employment in 15–24 age group. *Source:* created by the authors.

Indeed, there are some surprising and marked differences compared to the relationships shown in Figure 2. In terms of similarities, rising incomes in sub-Saharan Africa lead to both higher urbanization and lower infant mortality, although the latter effect is much weaker in Africa than in the rest of the developing world. Lower infant mortality, in turn, has a somewhat stronger effect on reducing desired family size in Africa than in other developing countries, but a much weaker effect on birth spacing. Higher levels of urbanization are associated with higher levels of female education and employment, with effects of approximately the same magnitude in Africa as in other developing regions.

However, there are substantial differences in the outcomes of female education and female employment. Outside Africa, many factors contribute directly to longer birth intervals and thus lower fertility – including lower infant mortality, higher income, women’s education, young women’s employment, total women’s employment, and urbanization. Among these, *women’s employment*, both for young women and for all women, has the largest direct effect.

In sub-Saharan Africa, however, *women’s education* is the most powerful factor driving changes in birth intervals. Women’s employment – whether for young women or for all

women – has no statistically significant effect at all. Moreover, in sub-Saharan Africa, but not in other developing regions, women's education also has a significant direct effect on desired family size. Another unusual finding is that in sub-Saharan Africa, unlike in other developing regions, income growth and urbanization have no direct effect on fertility, acting only indirectly through increases in women's education.

Discussion

In sum, sub-Saharan Africa is different. In other developing regions, a cluster of modernizing changes work together to reinforce behaviors that lengthen birth intervals and thus reduce fertility. Most notably, women are increasingly entering the workforce. Women's education, however, has only a modest effect on birth intervals and no significant impact on desired family size. In sub-Saharan Africa, by contrast, women's education is absolutely central – it is the most important driver of changes in birth intervals and also has a strong direct effect on reducing desired family size. Female employment, on the other hand, has no significant effect on fertility, neither through family size nor through birth intervals.

How is this possible? We propose an explanation rooted in traditional socioeconomic roles and behaviors. In most developing countries before modernization, men were the main breadwinners and bore the bulk of agricultural labor, while women were responsible for various, mostly unpaid, household tasks, including childcare. As modernization progressed and women began entering paid employment outside the home, they faced a trade-off between spending more time working and earning income, and staying home to care for their children.

In Tropical Africa, the traditional division of labor was fundamentally different, as many societies in the region practiced hoe agriculture (as opposed to the plow agriculture common in other regions such as North Africa, Asia, and Latin America). In hoe agriculture, women are responsible for most of the fieldwork, which meant that women traditionally had to work outside the home. The necessity of spending long hours working in the fields while simultaneously caring for children led to the early development of various 'support networks.' Extended families established their own 'childcare systems' that allowed women to avoid the trade-off between work and childcare. In many African cultures, it was expected that aunts, siblings, grandparents, cousins, and even co-wives (in polygynous societies) would 'take shifts' to help care for children while mothers worked.

As a result, the emergence and expansion of new occupations requiring women to work outside the home did not produce a similar fertility-inhibiting effect as seen elsewhere, because traditional practices of sharing childcare among extended family members remained (and in many cases still remain) in place. As Korotayev et al. (2016: 259) note:

"As long as extended families provide working women – not only those in agriculture but also women employed in urban paid jobs – with relatives willing to assist with household tasks and childcare, paid female employment may contribute far less to fertility decline in Tropical Africa than observed in other regions. In fact, it may even delay fertility reduction by slowing the shift toward a nuclear family system."

These cultural patterns thus buffer the impact of women's employment on childbearing. Consequently, women's employment should have no significant effect on birth spacing or fertility in Tropical Africa, which is exactly what we observe in the path model.

The factor most central to fertility decline in Tropical Africa appears to be women's education. Moreover, our path analysis shows that other developmental changes seem to influence fertility primarily through their effects on female education. This aligns with Bongaarts' (2017) findings, where multiple regression analyses revealed that, when total fertility, contraceptive prevalence, and desired family size are regressed on education, income, life expectancy, and urbanization, only education consistently remains significant. Therefore, to understand future fertility trends in Africa, it is crucial to closely examine progress in female education.

Unfortunately, the available data on girls' primary and secondary school enrollment in Tropical Africa paints a disappointing picture. Overall, net secondary attendance for females in sub-Saharan Africa stands at only 34% – half the level seen in the Middle East and North Africa, and nearly a quarter lower than in South Asia. Table 1 presents female primary and secondary enrollment rates for major Tropical African countries (UNICEF 2018). While the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) spurred progress in girls' primary enrollment – although most countries in the region still fell short of the 100% target – substantial gaps persist in female secondary education. Even in countries with female primary attendance rates above 80%, such as Tanzania, Burundi, Uganda, and Rwanda, secondary attendance remains at roughly 25% or lower.

Table 1. Africa's secondary education gap, 2023

	Primary education	Secondary education	Total fertility rate
Niger	46	13	6.7
Burkina Faso	50	17	4.7
Nigeria	66	49	5.1
Ethiopia	67	18	4.1
Sudan	67	45	4.4
Central African Republic	68	15	5.9
Angola	76	17	5.2
Tanzania	83	25	4.7
Burundi	84	14	5.0
Dem. Rep. Congo	85	41	6.1
Kenya	87	44	3.3
Uganda	87	21	4.5
Malawi	95	34	3.8
Rwanda	96	23	3.7

Source: World Bank. World Development Indicators. *Note:* Female net attendance ratio, primary and secondary education, %, 2023, in selected Tropical African countries. Total fertility rates in these countries are provided for reference.

It is important to emphasize that female education is a necessary condition for fertility decline, but it is not fully sufficient on its own. This becomes evident when comparing Nigeria, Kenya, and Rwanda. Nigeria and Kenya both have relatively high female secondary en-

rollment rates – almost twice as high as Rwanda's. Yet, Kenya and Rwanda have made much greater progress in their fertility transitions than Nigeria. While these differences warrant more detailed research, we can tentatively attribute them to factors such as vigorous national family planning campaigns with a focus on rural outreach and teenage marriage bans in Rwanda, and strong vocal support from religious leaders in Kenya (see, e.g., Rybalkina 2023), contrasted with their absence in Nigeria (Rybalkina 2024).

Why does secondary female education appear less effective in driving fertility decline in Nigeria? First, unlike Rwanda and Kenya, Nigeria lacks a large-scale, coordinated family planning campaign, making it more representative of the typical Tropical African case, while Rwanda and Kenya stand out as exceptions with their relative success. Second, the quality of education remains a persistent challenge across many countries in the region (Pritchett 2013). The relative 'value' of a year of schooling in Tropical Africa is significantly lower than in European countries or the USA. This means secondary education is especially critical: women who leave school after primary education – typically completed by age 12 or 13 – are vulnerable to early marriage and lack the skills to earn an independent income or negotiate within their households. By contrast, women who complete secondary school are less likely to marry before age 18, have greater agency in making fertility decisions, and contribute more economically to their families, which raises their status within the household (Jejeebhoy 1995).

Indeed, as Hertrich (2017) has argued, women in Africa face particular challenges in asserting control over their reproductive choices. Many are married young to much older men or must navigate competition with co-wives in polygamous marriages, situations in which they are often poorly positioned to influence decisions about family size (Rybalkina 2023, 2024). Furthermore, the extended family child-support system places additional pressure on women to have more children, since both the benefits and costs of larger families are shared across the extended family network rather than solely by the spousal couple (Hertrich 2017; Johnson-Hanks 2007 Mbacké 2017). Completing secondary education equips young women with the skills and confidence necessary to resist these pressures and empowers them to make decisions to limit childbearing if they choose. Joel Cohen (2008: 572) highlights the importance of secondary education in high-fertility societies, stating:

“Although there are other factors at work, in many developing countries, women who complete secondary school have, on average, at least one fewer child over their lifetime compared to women who complete only primary school. For example, in Niger in 1998, women with secondary education had 31% fewer children (an average of 4.6) than those who completed only primary education (6.7 children). Similarly, in Yemen in 1997, women with primary education had an average of 4.6 children, whereas those who completed secondary school averaged 3.1 children. In some sub-Saharan African societies, a reduction in lifetime fertility is observed only among girls who have completed 10 or more years of schooling.”

These challenges are not unique to Tropical Africa; they are also present in many developing regions, especially South Asia, where fertility rates have nonetheless declined significantly. However, as our path analysis demonstrates, educational progress plays a much more critical role in fertility decline in Tropical Africa than in other regions. As illustrated in Figure 2, in most developing countries, women's employment tends to have a greater impact on reducing fertility than women's education. In contrast, in sub-Saharan Africa, the reverse is true – women's education is the stronger driver of fertility decline, while female employment shows little to no effect.

Conclusion

In sum, Tropical Africa stands apart from other regions. While increases in female employment have been pivotal to fertility declines elsewhere, such effects are minimal here. The persistently high fertility in Tropical Africa stems from its unique extended family systems and a significant shortfall in secondary education, compounded by the absence of widespread family planning campaigns – especially those backed by influential local figures like religious leaders and aimed at rural communities. Without addressing these core issues, further gains in primary education, urbanization, or income per capita are likely to produce only modest reductions in fertility. Given the rapid mortality declines already achieved and the persistently high fertility, Tropical Africa is poised for continued rapid population growth in the coming decades.

References

- Benefo KD (1995) The determinants of the duration of postpartum sexual abstinence in West Africa: A multilevel analysis. *Demography* 32 (2): 139–57. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2061737>.
- Bongaarts J (2010) The causes of educational differences in fertility in sub-Saharan Africa. *Vienna Yearbook of Population Research* 8: 31–50. <https://doi.org/10.1553/populationyearbook2010s31>.
- Bongaarts J (2017) Africa's Unique Fertility Transition. *Population and Development Review* 43 (S1): 39–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2016.00164.x>.
- Bongaarts J, Casterline JB (2013) Fertility transition: Is sub-Saharan Africa different? *Population and Development Review* 38 (S1): 153–168. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2013.00557.x>.
- Caldwell JC, Caldwell P (1987) The cultural context of high fertility in sub-Saharan Africa. *Population and Development Review* 13 (3): 409–37. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1973133>.
- Caldwell JC, Caldwell P (2002) Africa: the new family planning frontier. *Studies in Family Planning* 33 (1): 76–86. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4465.2002.00076.x>.
- Caldwell JC, Orubuloye IO, Caldwell P (1992) Fertility decline in Africa: A new type of transition? *Population and Development Review* 18 (2): 211–42. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1973678>.
- Casterline JB (2017) Prospects for Fertility Decline in Africa. *Population and Development Review* 43 (S1): 3–18. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padr.12055>.
- Casterline JB, Agyei-Mensah S (2017) Fertility desires and the course of fertility decline in sub-Saharan Africa. *Population and Development Review* 43 (S1): 84–111. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padr.12030>.
- Casterline JB, Odden C (2016) Trends in inter-birth intervals in developing countries, 1965–2014. *Population and Development Review* 42 (2): 173–94. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1728-4457.2016.00134.x>.
- Cohen JE (2008) Make secondary education universal. *Nature* 456: 572–3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/456572a>.
- Duflo E (2001) Schooling and Labor-Market Consequences of School Construction in Indonesia: Evidence from an unusual policy experiment. *American Economic Review* 91 (4): 795–813. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.91.4.795>.
- Ezeh A, Mberu B, Emina J (2009) Stall in fertility decline in Eastern African countries: Regional analysis of patterns, determinants and implications. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* 364: 2991–3007. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2009.0166>.
- Feng Y, Kugler J, Zak PJ (2000) The politics of fertility and economic development. *International Studies Quarterly* 44: 667–93. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3014037>.

- Garenne M (2018) Family planning and fertility decline in Africa: From 1950 to 2010. In: Amarin ZO (Ed.) *Family Planning*. Intech, London. https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.71029_
- Goujon A, Lutz W, Samir KC (2015) Education stalls and subsequent stalls in African fertility: A descriptive overview. *Demographic Research* 33: 1281–96. <https://doi.org/10.4054/DemRes.2015.33.47>.
- Guengant J-P, May JF (2013) African demography. *Global Journal of Emerging Market Economies* 5 (3): 215–67. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0974910113505792>.
- Hertrich V (2017) Trends in age at marriage at the onset of fertility transition in sub-Saharan Africa. *Population and Development Review* 43 (S1): 112–37. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padr.12043>.
- Ivanov SF (2017) Determinants of the demographic transition in the Global South. *Demographic Review* 4 (2): 6–52. <https://doi.org/10.17323/demreview.v4i2.7102> (In Russ.)
- Ivanov SF (2020) Determinants and Consequences of Population Trends in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Journal of the Institute for African Studies* 4: 55–76. <https://doi.org/10.31132/2412-5717-2020-53-4-55-76> (In Russ.)
- Jejeebhoy SJ (1995) *Women's Education, Autonomy, and Reproductive Behaviour: Experience from Developing Countries*. Clarendon Press, Oxford.
- Johnson-Hanks J (2007) Natural intentions: Fertility decline in the African Demographic and Health Surveys. *American Journal of Sociology* 112 (4): 1008–43. <https://doi.org/10.1086/508791>.
- Keats A (2018) Women's Schooling, Fertility, and Child Health Outcomes: Evidence from Uganda's Free Primary Education Program. *Journal of Development Economics* 135: 142–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2018.07.002>.
- Kokole OH (1994) The politics of fertility in Africa. *Population and Development Review* 20 (Suppl.): 73–88. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2807940>
- Korotayev A, Zinkina J, Goldstone JA, Shulgin S (2016) Explaining current fertility dynamics in tropical Africa from an anthropological perspective: A cross-cultural investigation. *Cross Cultural Research* 50 (3): 251–80. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1069397116644158>.
- Lesthaeghe R (1980) On the social control of human reproduction. *Population and Development Review* 6 (4): 527–48. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1972925>.
- Mbacké C (2017) The persistence of high fertility in sub-Saharan Africa: A Comment. *Population and Development Review* 43 (S1): 330–7. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padr.12052>.
- Moultreie TA, Sayi TS, Timæus IM (2012) Birth intervals, postponement, and fertility decline: A new type of transition? *Population Studies* 66 (3): 241–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00324728.2012.701660>.
- Osili UO, Long BT (2008) Does Female Schooling Reduce Fertility? Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Development Economics* 87 (1): 57–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2007.10.003>.
- Pritchett LH (1994) Desired Fertility and the Impact of Population Policies. *Population and Development Review* 20 (1): 1–55. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2137629>.
- Pritchett LH (2013) *The Rebirth of Education: Schooling Ain't Learning*. Center for Global Development, Washington D.C.
- Rybalkina IG (2023) The problem of restructuring reproductive behavior in Kenya. *Vostok (Oriens)* 1: 63–75. <https://doi.org/10.31857/S086919080020572-6> (In Russ.)
- Rybalkina IG (2024) On the issue of family planning in Nigeria. *Vostok (Oriens)* 2: 122–33. <https://doi.org/10.31857/S086919080029678-2> (In Russ.)
- Shapiro D, Gebreselassie T (2008) Fertility transition in sub-Saharan Africa: Falling and stalling. *African Population Studies* 23 (1): 3–23. https://doi.org/10.11564/23-1-310_
- Shapiro D, Hinde A (2017) On the pace of fertility decline in sub-Saharan Africa. *Demographic Research* 37: 1327–38. <https://doi.org/10.4054/DemRes.2017.37.40>.

Shapiro D, Kreider A, Varner C, Sinha M (2013) Stalling of fertility transitions and socioeconomic change in the developing world: Evidence from the Demographic and Health Surveys. In: Tabutin D, Masquelier B (Eds) *Ralentissements, résistances et ruptures dans les transitions démographiques*, Actes de la Chaire Quetelet 2010. Presse de l'Université de Louvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, 47–64.

Other sources of information

UNICEF Global Databases (<https://data.unicef.org/topic/education/overview/>)

United Nations (2011) *World Population Prospects, the 2010 Revision*. Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division. URL: https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/publications/pdf/trends/WPP2010/WPP2010_Volume-I_Comprehensive-Tables.pdf

United Nations (2024) *World Population Prospects, the 2024 Revision*. Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division. URL: <https://population.un.org/wpp/>

World Bank. *World Development Indicators* (<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/>)

World Bank. *Constant GDP per capita: All Income Levels for Sub-Saharan Africa*, retrieved from: FRED, Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis <https://fred.stlouisfed.org/series/NYGDPPCAPKDSSF>

Acknowledgements

This article is an output of a research project conducted within the Basic Research Program at HSE University in 2025, supported by the Russian Science Foundation (Project Number 24-18-00650).

Information about the authors

- Yuliya Viktorovna Zinkina – Doctor of Economics, Leading Research Fellow of the Center for Stability and Risk Analysis at HSE University, Research Fellow at the Faculty of Global Studies, Lomonosov Moscow State University. Moscow, 101000, Russia. E-mail: juliazin@list.ru
- Jack A. Goldstone – PhD, Virginia E. and John T. Hazel, Jr., Professor; Director of the Center for the Study of Social Change, Institutions, and Policy, George Mason University. Arlington, 22201, USA. E-mail: jgoldsto@gmu.edu
- Sergey Georgievich Shulgin – Candidate of Economics, Head of Research and Development, zypl.ai. Dubai, 00000 DIFC, United Arab Emirates. E-mail: sergey@shulgin.ru
- Andrey Vitalievich Korotayev – Doctor of Sciences (History), Director of the Center for Stability and Risk Analysis at HSE University, Chief Research Fellow of the Institute for African Studies of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Moscow, 101000, Russia. E-mail: akorotayev@gmail.com

Appendix

Lists of Sub-Saharan and Other Developing Countries Included in the Samples

The following Sub-Saharan African countries were included in the sample: Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Burundi, Cameroon, Cape Verde, Central African Republic, Chad, Comoros, Congo (Republic), Congo (Democratic Republic), Côte d'Ivoire, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, São Tomé and Príncipe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Africa, Sudan, Swaziland, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia, and Zimbabwe.

The following other developing countries were included in the sample: Albania, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bangladesh, Bolivia, Brazil, Cambodia, Colombia, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador, Georgia, Guatemala, Guyana, Haiti, Honduras, India, Indonesia, Jamaica, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyz Republic, Maldives, Mexico, Moldova, Nepal, Nicaragua, Pakistan, Paraguay, Peru, Philippines, Romania, Sri Lanka, Tajikistan, Thailand, Timor-Leste, Trinidad and Tobago, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine, Uzbekistan, Vietnam, and Yemen.